

EFFECT OF HEAT TREATMENT TEMPERATURE ON YOUNG'S MODULUS AND INTERNAL FRICTION OF C/C COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

As baseline mechanical properties, Young's modulus and internal friction of C/C composites were precisely studied using a newly developed internal friction apparatus in a vacuum with lateral vibration method from room temperature up to 1373 K. The objective of this study is to establish clear understanding of those properties through correlation between microstructure and those properties. Unidirectional C/C composites reinforced with mesophase pitch-based carbon fibers were selected and were heat treated with temperatures ranged from 1473 K to 2773 K prior to the internal friction measurement.

Young's modulus at room temperature was increased with increasing heat treatment (HT) temperature. From the Arrhenius plots of both Young's modulus and internal friction, the apparent active energies were obtained to be about 130 kJ/mol. The positive temperature dependence of Young's modulus gradually decreased to null with increasing HT temperature and turns to negative after the HT at 2773 K.

Keywords:

unidirectional composites, C/C composites, Young's modulus, heat treatment temperature, internal friction, temperature dependence, lateral vibration

1. Introduction

One of the most important R & D efforts of carbon fiber reinforced carbon composites (C/C composites) has been a development of high performance C/C composites where elastic modulus is one of the important baseline mechanical properties for evaluation. Although there have been a strong demand for the exact evaluation of elastic modulus, most of the methods used have been insufficient from their limitations of accuracy, temperature for measurement, environments, etc. Owing to our recent efforts to develop internal friction measurement apparatus [1], measurements of accurate dynamic elastic properties up to 1373 K were carried out. The important motivation is to obtain a clear and precise understanding about temperature dependence of Young's modulus for there have been many reports on this subject including reverse temperature dependences, such as positive dependence in isotropic graphite [2] and negative dependence in carbon fibers [3]. In general, mechanistic studies about mechanical properties have been performed correlating with microstructural behavior. This paper concentrates to provide internal friction results and microstructural information is provided elsewhere [3].

For carbon materials, the importance of HT on their properties is well-known, however, there have been no systematic studies, thus there is no clear understanding of this effect. Another objective of this investigation is to present a correlation between Young's modulus and microstructure of C/C composites under a variety of heat treatments.

2. Experimental

2.1. Materials Used

Materials used were unidirectionally reinforced C/C composites, reinforced with mesophase pitch-based carbon fibers. Unidirectional prepreg sheets were produced by a drum winding method using a mixture of green cokes and phenolic resin (80/20). Those sheets were stacked and preformed at 423 K by a hot press method. Then, they were heat treated at 1473 K in a nitrogen atmosphere. The final heat treatment was done at 1673, 1873, 2073, 2273 or 2773 K in argon. The characteristics of the materials used are shown in Table 1. The specimens for internal friction measurement with the specimen dimensions of 1 mm in thickness, 5 mm in width and 80 mm in length were cut out aligned to the fiber direction parallel to the longitudinal axis of the specimen.

Table 1. Characteristics of the C/C composites used.

Reinforcement	Mesophase pitch-based carbon fiber (Heat Treatment Temp. : 2473 K) Young's Modulus : 500 GPa	
Matrix precursor resin	Green Coke : 80 % Phenolic Resin : 20 %	
Heat Treatment Temperature (HTT)	Vf (%)	Density ($\times 10^3 \text{ Kg/m}^3$)
1473 K	45.2	1.62
1673 K	45.1	1.68
1873 K	45.0	1.68
2073 K	45.9	1.71
2273 K	46.6	1.71
2773 K	48.9	1.82

2.2. Internal Friction Measurement

Internal friction measurement was carried out utilizing the recently developed lateral vibration type internal friction apparatus by electrostatic capacitance method with an advanced high temperature capability and clean vacuum [1]. Young's modulus of C/C composites was determined from resonant frequency and internal friction value was determined from free damping behavior under lateral vibration with an strain amplitude about 10^{-5} . The temperature range for this measurement was from 298 K (room temperature;RT) to 1373 K and a vacuum quality at RT was 2×10^{-5} Pa.

2.3. Structural Inspection

Macroscopic structure, including fiber volume fraction, was inspected by both optical microscopy and scanning electron microscopy. Microstructural inspections were performed with X-ray diffraction analysis, transmission electron microscopy (TEM) and Raman spectroscopy. X-ray diffraction analysis was done by micro-probe XRD analyzer. Other inspections by high resolution TEM and by Raman spectroscopy can be seen elsewhere [4,5].

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Elastic Property at Room Temperature

Young's moduli at RT after a variety of final heat treatment from 1473 K to 2773 K are summarized in Figure 1. With increasing heat treatment temperature (HTT), Young's modulus gradually increased with rather steeper increment at higher HTTs. The very slow increase at lower than 2273 K might be related with the final heat treatment temperature of carbon fibers at 2473 K. That is the effect of HT on their value lower than 2273 might arise from the microstructural changes in matrix and not in fibers. The large increase seen in the specimens with HTT of 2773 K seems to correspond this interpretation, accounting the potential increase of Young's modulus in the fibers. The results obtained from the specimens with HTT lower than 2473 K were lower than 250 MPa which is roughly meets the simple rule of mixture value from the data seen in Table 1. There is no clear insights about this low elastic property but there might be some effects from porosity in the matrix and microstructural characteristics of the matrix on the way from carbonization to full graphitization. The same tendency on theoretically identical materials has been reported by Takayasu *et al.* [6]. There have been many reports on microstructural changes in carbon and graphite at this temperature range and many models about graphitization process have been proposed. These models stand on the assumption that the process is thermally activated. At this point we have the same position to analyze the material behavior under the final heat treatment. That is, the elastic property change can be written as follows.

$$E_{HTT} - E_{1473} = E_0 \cdot \exp\left(-\frac{H_1}{R \cdot HTT}\right) \quad (1)$$

where, E_{HTT} , E_0 , H_1 and R are modulus of specimen after HT at $T = HTT$, constant, activation energy and gas constant, respectively.

The Arrhenius plots of the Young's modulus change as a function of HTT are shown in Figure 2. From this figure, apparent activation energy can be obtained to be 122 kJ/mol. In comparison with the activation energies of graphitization known, such as 1130 kJ/mol and 300 kJ/mol for pyrolytic carbon and glassy carbon, respectively, the value of 122 kJ/mol is quite smaller than expected. These values suggest that the microstructure change during this heat treatment might not be any kind of graphitization including long range reactions. Although, there is no basis to prove, but the possible mechanism seems to be some types of coalescence of fine graphite particle and alignment of lattice along c-axis.

Figure 1. Dependence of Young's modulus at RT on HTT in C/C composites.

Figure 2. Arrhenius plots of Young's modulus changes at RT.

3.2. Internal Friction at Room Temperature

Temperature dependence of internal friction in C/C composite after HT at 1473 K is shown in Figure 3. Relatively steep decrease of internal friction up to 800 K and the following steady state behavior of internal friction at higher than that temperature can be clearly recognized. From this temperature spectrum, as a trial, steady state value at higher than 800 K was treated as athermal component of the internal friction (Q_{ath}^{-1}) and the rest was counted as thermal component of it (Q_{th}^{-1}). These are drawn by two dotted lines in the figure. The thermal component looks like a relaxation peak, but there is no basis to make such conclusion and cannot be conclusive, at this point. Because we have no basis to determine the possible peak value of the thermal component, $Q_{th}^{-1}(HTT)$ at RT was presented as the representing value in Table 2, which summarizes Q_{ath}^{-1} and Q_{th}^{-1} with variations of HTT. Q_{ath}^{-1} is relatively a small portion of the internal friction and is recognized to be mainly due to the condition of specimen setting to the apparatus, thus the attention is only paid for Q_{th}^{-1} , hereafter. The monotonic decrease of Q_{th}^{-1} with increasing HTT suggests that this tendency can be related with microstructural changes from carbonized state to graphitic structure. As the $Q_{th}^{-1}(1473)$ can be denoted as the initial stage of graphitization from carbonized state, subtraction of $Q_{th}^{-1}(HTT)$ from $Q_{th}^{-1}(1473)$ is counted as the effect of microstructural change on internal friction value. If the origin of the thermal component of internal friction would be line defects, such as dislocations, Q_{th}^{-1} should be proportional with effective line defect density, which is an averaged defect density value of many types of line defects. Under the assumption of uniform formation of line defects in the material during the HTs, the effective line defect density should be ruled by 1/3 power law of the microstructural change. Now, as

Figure 3. Temperature dependence of internal friction in C/C composites after HT at 1473 K.

Table 2. Athermal and thermal components of internal friction at RT.

Heat Treatment Temperature (HTT)	Q_{ath}^{-1} ($\times 10^{-4}$)	Q_{th}^{-1} at RT ($\times 10^{-4}$)
1473 K	1.344	5.487
1673 K	0.862	4.325
1873 K	0.867	3.441
2073 K	0.597	3.105
2273 K	0.621	2.571
2773 K	0.873	0.933

the identical analogy with the Young's modulus change, effect of HT on Q_{th}^{-1} can be formulated as follows.

$$(Q_{th}^{-1}(HTT) - Q_{th}^{-1}(1473))^3 = Q_0^{-1} \cdot \exp\left(-\frac{H_2}{R \cdot HTT}\right) \quad (2)$$

where, $Q_{th}^{-1}(HTT)$, Q_0^{-1} , H_2 and R are $Q_{th}^{-1}(HTT)$ at RT, constant, activation energy and gas constant, respectively.

From the Arrhenius plots of the internal friction changes, shown in Figure 4, apparent activation energy can be derived to be 136 kJ/mol. This value is quite close to the value of 122 kJ/mol obtained from the Young's modulus change. This is a good coincidence that both phenomena are strongly related with microstructural change by high temperature heat treatment.

3.3. Microstructure Inspection by X-ray Diffraction Analysis

To understand the microstructural evolution under high temperature heat treatment, high resolution TEM inspection and Raman spectroscopy were applied to the materials used in this work. The former results provided clear evidence of

graphitization by HT at 2773 K but were difficult to get quantitative information about graphitization behavior [4]. As to the latter, again, quantitative evaluation was quite difficult at the temperature range of interest [5]. Thus, this paper only provides the results from X-ray diffraction analysis of the materials used. With increasing HTT, 002 and 004 peaks of graphite became sharp which suggests the enhancement of graphitization. Figure 5 is enlarged portion of the XRD pattern from 40 to 60 of 2θ value. 100 and 101 peaks seen for the case of HT at 2773 K is not detectable for the cases of HT at lower than 2773 K, where so called 10 peak from turbostratic structure can be identified. These data seem to support the mechanistic interpretation done at the later part of section 3.1..

Figure 4. Arrhenius plots of thermal component of internal friction changes at RT.

Figure 5. X-ray diffraction patterns of heat treated C/C composites.

3.4. Temperature Dependence of Young's Modulus

There has been two way dependences of Young's modulus on test temperature for carbon and graphitic materials including C/C composites. Typical examples are shown in Figure 6, where Rowe *et al.*'s results on carbon fiber indicates negative dependence and Eto *et al.*'s results on isotropic graphite indicates positive dependence. Therefore, to clarify the origin of these differences is an very urgent and important issue to C/C composites. Figure 7 summarizes test temperature dependence of Young's modulus. There can be seen a slight but positive temperature dependence in specimens with HTT lower than 2073 K. For the case of HTT of 2273 K, Young's modulus is nearly independent on test temperature. But by the HT at 2773 K, temperature dependence becomes negative. And the absolute value of Young's modulus is monotonically increasing with increasing HTT. In order to identify the effect of HT, Young's modulus change by HT is normalized and presented in Figure 8. In this figure, positive temperature dependence can be clearly seen for the cases of HTT lower than 2073 K, and a slight but positive dependence can be seen for the case of HT at 2273 K. Another important feature for this case is that, at higher test temperature, there is a tiny turn over from positive to negative dependence. This seems to be the transient phenomenon from positive to negative dependence. After HT at 2773 K, a clear temperature dependence with monotonic decrease, that is negative dependence, can be seen. From the fact that the positive temperature dependence of Young's modulus is a typical feature for the case of elasticity controlled by entropy, the cases of HTT lower than 2273 K maintaining a lots of misalignment of c-axis seem feasible to behave like polymer or rubber. On the contrary, specimen with HT at 2773 K, microstructure dominated by graphitic structure is rationalized to behave like elasticity controlled by energy. These results emphasize the importance of microstructural information to predict temperature dependence of Young's modulus and internal friction.

Figure 6. Dependence of normalized Young's modulus on test temperature in carbon materials [2,3].

Figure 7. Dependence of Young's modulus on test temperature in C/C composites.

Figure 8. Effect of HT on temperature dependence of normalized Young's modulus.

4. Conclusions

As baseline mechanical properties, Young's modulus and internal friction of C/C composites were precisely studied using a newly developed internal friction apparatus in a vacuum with lateral vibration method from room temperature up to 1373 K. The conclusions can be summarized as follows.

(1) Young's modulus and thermal component of internal friction at RT were increased and decreased respectively with increasing HTT. From the Arrhenius plots of them, the apparent active energy was obtained to be about 130 kJ/mol.

(2) From X-ray diffraction analysis, microstructural change by high temperature heat treatment seems to be some type of coalescence of fine graphite particle and alignment of lattice along c-axis. And the change is strongly related with changes of Young's modulus and internal friction at RT with increasing HTT.

(3) The positive temperature dependence of Young's modulus gradually decreased to null with increasing HT temperature and turns to negative after the HT at 2773 K.

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